

Electrochemical investigations on some 1-carboxymethylpyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-[4'-sulfonamoyl]azopyrazoles

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The electrochemical behavior of 1-carboxymethylpyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-[4'-sulfonamoyl]azopyrazoles has been studied on the basis of d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry and coulometry in Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5–12.0. The electroreduction occurs in a single, well defined, $2e$ step at dropping mercury electrode. At glassy carbon electrode also one $2e$ cathodic peak is observed. The electrode process is diffusion-controlled and irreversible in nature. A reaction mechanism has been postulated. The effects of ionic strength, cations, anions and solvent composition have also been evaluated.

Pyrazole is one of the important classes of heterocyclic compounds possessing a wide spectrum of biological activities¹. The study of the mechanism of reduction of various compounds of physiological importance at various electrodes often parallels the metabolism of these compounds². Therefore, the electrochemical studies have been carried out on newly synthesized 1-carboxymethylpyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-[sulfonamoyl]azopyrazoles.

Results and discussion

D.C. polarography :

In all the pyrazoles the possible reduction sites are C=C, C=N and -N=N-. The unsubstituted pyrazoles are not reducible at d.m.e. and G.C. electrodes under experimental conditions, whereas reduction of azo group³ is characterized by the well-defined, two-electron reduction wave in B.R. buffers. Electrochemical characteristics of the compounds are compiled in Table 1.

The diffusion-controlled character was verified by linear plots of i_d vs concentration of depolarizer and i_d vs square-root of mercury reservoir height (\sqrt{h}). It is further confirmed by low temperature-coefficient (below 1.62% K⁻¹). Irreversibility of the electrode process was ascertained by

Table 1. Electrochemical characteristics of 1-carboxymethylpyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-[4'-sulfonamoyl]azopyrazoles

pH = 6.5, conc. = 2.0×10^{-4} M, height = 60 cm

Sl. no.	R	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μ A	$-E_p$ V	i_{pc} μ A	$\frac{\partial E_{1/2}}{\partial pH}$	αn_a	P	I^*
1.	H	0.56	1.80	0.70	4.70	0.115	0.369	0.7180	3.60
2.		0.68	2.10	0.66	4.20	0.110	0.369	0.6248	4.34
3.		0.62	1.65	0.68	3.03	0.074	0.430	0.6390	3.44
4.		0.60	1.72	0.73	4.10	0.135	0.323	0.7380	3.30
5.		0.58	1.65	0.73	3.50	0.100	0.430	0.7280	3.30
6.		0.68	1.65	0.64	4.60	0.150	0.323	0.8200	3.30

* I^* (diffusion current constant) = $\frac{i_d}{C_m^{2/3} t^{1/6}}$ where C is the concentration of depolarizer, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ is capillary characteristics (Ref. 5).

the shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with increasing concentration of the depolarizer. Moreover, logarithmic analysis and low values of α_n further confirmed the irreversible nature of electrode reaction. The $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards negative potential with rise in pH upto 8.0 and thereafter remained practically constant. It suggests participation of proton in electrode process⁴. The number of protons (p) involved in the rate-determining step is calculated from the slope of plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH and $\log i/i_d$ vs E using expressions^{5,6},

$$\frac{\partial E_{1/2}}{\partial \text{pH}} = \frac{0.05917}{\alpha n_a} P$$

$$\alpha n_a = \frac{0.05917}{E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}}$$

where α is transfer coefficient and n_a is number of electrons involved in the reduction process.

Linear sweep and cyclic voltammetry :

In cyclic voltammograms, the absence of anodic peak and shift of cathodic peak towards negative peak potential with increasing sweep rate [v, 50–200 mV] confirm the irreversible nature of the electrode process. The linear plots of i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ and i_p vs concentration passing through origin, suggest the diffusion-controlled nature of electrode process⁶. The peak potential shifts towards negative potential upto pH 8.0 and after that there is practical constancy in E_p with pH.

Coulometry and product analysis :

The number of electrons involved in the electrode process was determined by electrolysis at slightly higher than peak potential and found to be 2. During electrolysis, electronic spectra of the solution were recorded at different time-intervals. The λ_{max} at 415 nm (-N=N-) showed a decrease in peak intensity after each intervals of electrolysis and finally disappeared confirming the reduction of -N=N- group. The negative dye test indicates that -N=N- group is reducing upto -NH-NH- stage only. After complete controlled potential electrolysis (nearly 12 h), the reduced solution was examined by TLC and found to contain one product. The electrolyzed solution did not give any polarographic wave. The electrolyzed solution showed λ_{max} at 280 nm confirming the presence of C=O group.

Reduction mechanism :

On the basis of the results the mechanism of reduction for these compounds at d.m.e. and G.C. electrodes is presented in Scheme 1, supported by the studies of previous workers⁷.

Effect of ionic strength :

The electrical double layer influences the electrode process due to its effect on the surface concentration of depolarizer and on the kinetics of electrode reaction. The

Scheme 1

following is the relationship⁸ between $E_{1/2}$ and ψ_1 for irreversible electrode process,

$$E_{1/2} = \Delta\psi_1 \left[\frac{\alpha n_a - Z}{\alpha n_a} \frac{\partial E_{1/2}}{\partial \text{pH}} \frac{F}{2.303 RT} \right]$$

where ψ_1 is the variation in the double layer potential, α the transfer coefficient, Z the charge on the ion, n_a the number of electrons transferred in rate-determining step.

Polarograms were recorded using varying concentrations of KCl. With ionic strength no change in half-wave potential and wave height was observed. As the compounds under study, like most of other organic compounds, absorbed at mercury surface and their preprotonation is also of surface nature, i.e. they are present in solution chiefly in the non-ionised state, RH^+ occurs only before the discharge on electrode surface. Thus electrostatic field of electrode will have no effect on the distribution of concentration of arylazopyrazoles at the electrode and Z in the above equation should be considered as zero, hence first term in bracket become equal to unity. As the second term in bracket of the above equation is approximately 1, so $E_{1/2} = 0$, which was observed with change in the ionic strength of supporting electrolyte (Table 2).

Effect of cations and anions :

For evaluating the effect of cations, the parent compound was polarographed using LiCl, KCl and tetramethylammonium bromide as supporting electrolytes.

In all the cases the usual one well-defined wave was observed. The shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with increase in size of cations (Table 3) may be due to the change of the structure of double layer^{8,9}.

The value of $E_{1/2}$ was found to be independent of ψ_1 ; ionic strength for a particular supporting electrolyte could vary from one electrolyte to other. Increase in size of cations led to the decrease in ψ_1 , making the reaction more difficult¹⁰, resulting in negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ values. Polarograms with supporting electrolyte having a common cation and different anions, show no change in $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values, as to be expected, since cations predominates in electrical double layer at these potentials¹¹.

Table 2. Effect of ionic strength on polarographic characteristics of 1-carboxymethylpyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-[4'-sulfonamoyl]azopyrazole

pH = 6.5, conc. $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, height = 60 cm

Sl. no.	Vol. of 1.0 M KCl ml	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA
1.	0.50	0.56	1.80
2.	1.00	0.56	1.80
3.	1.50	0.56	1.80
4.	2.00	0.56	1.80

Table 3. Effect of cations and anions on the polarographic characteristics of the arylazopyrazoles

pH = 6.5, conc. $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, height = 60 cm

Sl. no.	Supporting electrolyte	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA
1.	LiCl	0.50	1.80
2.	NaCl	0.54	1.80
3.	KCl	0.56	1.80
4.	$(C_2H_5)_4NBr^-$	0.60	1.80
5.	KBr	0.56	1.80
6.	KI	0.56	1.80
7.	KCl	0.56	1.80
8.	KNO_3	0.56	1.80

Effect of solvent composition :

The effect of solvent composition on wave characteristics was determined by recording polarograms of the compounds at pH 4.5 in varying DMF compositions (30–70%). With increase in DMF, $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards negative potential with decreasing i_d values (Table 4). At very high percentage of solvent the polarographic wave was very ill-defined. These effects may be ascribed partly due to the decrease in surface concentration of depolarizer and an increase in viscosity of the medium with an increase in the percentage of the non-aqueous solvent in aqueous organic mixture. A decrease in surface concentration would retard the electrode process¹² resulting in a decrease in half-wave potential and diffusion current. The viscosity values at different DMF compositions are summarized along with the

values of $i_d \sqrt{\eta}$ in Table 4. The deviation of this value from constancy is attributed to increase in solvation of depolarizer which results in decrease in diffusion coefficient.

Table 4. Effect of solvent composition on the polarographic characteristics of 1-carboxymethylpyridinium-3-aminophenyl-5-methyl-4-[4'-sulfonamoyl]azopyrazole

pH = 4.5, conc. $= 2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, height = 60 cm

Sl. no.	DMF%	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA	η cP	$i_d \sqrt{\eta}$
1.	30	0.48	1.87	1.23	-2.07
2.	40	0.52	1.78	1.27	-2.00
3.	50	0.56	1.60	1.32	-1.84
4.	60	0.58	1.52	1.35	-1.75
5.	70	0.60	1.08	1.44	-1.29

Experimental

All the substituted arylazopyrazoles were synthesized¹³ and their purity was ascertained by crystallization. Their structures were confirmed by elemental and spectral analyses. Stock solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of all the arylazopyrazoles were prepared in DMF (A.R.). KCl was used as a supporting electrolyte. B.R. buffers prepared. The equipment used and the experimental details are reported elsewhere².

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